

Unraveling Age and Gender Patterns in Orofacial Trauma

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Orofacial trauma is a common and often preventable public health issue. Vidarbha, a region in Maharashtra, India, has been reported to have a high incidence of orofacial trauma, attributed to various factors including road traffic accidents, interpersonal violence, and sports injuries. Understanding the incidence and patterns of orofacial trauma in Vidarbha is essential for developing effective preventive and management strategies.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted to determine the incidence of orofacial trauma over a 12-year period from 2012 to 2024 till date. Data was collected from records in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery department at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur. Information on age and gender was collected and analyzed.

Results: The incidence rate of orofacial trauma from Vidarbha region reporting to the institute were 343 cases, with a higher incidence among males (91%) than females (9%). Road traffic accidents were leading cause of orofacial fractures among the reported cases. Peak incidence of orofacial trauma was observed in young adults, typically between 2nd and 4th decade of life.

Conclusion: Orofacial trauma is a significant health issue, with road traffic accidents being the leading cause. Preventive strategies should focus on reducing the incidence of these fractures, particularly among high-risk groups such as young males. Additionally, improvements in trauma care and rehabilitation services are necessary to effectively manage orofacial fractures and reduce their impact on individuals and the healthcare system.

Keywords: *Orofacial trauma, maxillofacial trauma, retrospective analysis, incidence rate*

INTRODUCTION:

About 5–33% of patients with multiple traumas have maxillofacial trauma. [1-3] Because the maxillofacial region occupies a more prominent location in the human body, it is frequently injured. [4] It is becoming more common and is frequently observed in hospitalized assault, emergency, and accident cases.[5] Depending on the geographic area being evaluated, the etiology of orofacial trauma and injuries might vary, with locales within the same geographic area being mostly influenced by the socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental circumstances.[6] Researchers continue to debate this diversity since it is dependent on prevailing awareness, education on traffic laws, socioeconomic, cultural, and environmental factors.[4]

Numerous earlier studies have examined the causes and severity of maxillofacial injuries, which vary in frequency across India's various regions.[7] Numerous variables, such as traffic accidents, interpersonal aggression, and sports injuries, have been linked to the high frequency of orofacial trauma in the Vidarbha region of Maharashtra, India. Developing successful preventative and therapeutic measures requires an understanding of the

prevalence and trends of orofacial trauma in Vidarbha. The purpose of this retrospective study was to assess the distribution of orofacial trauma in the population with respect to age and gender.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A retrospective study was conducted to determine the incidence of orofacial trauma over a 12-year period from 2012 to 2024 till date. Data was collected from records in Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery department at Swargiya Dadasaheb Kalmegh Smruti Dental College and Hospital, Nagpur. A total of 1107 patients reported between the study period, out of which 343 patients reported back for the treatment. Information on age and gender was collected and analyzed. The manual search and data extraction from patient medical records served as the foundation for this investigation.

RESULTS:

A total of 343 patients reported to the Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery between January 2012 and April 2024 with patients reduced during the pandemic period. Incidence rate, Age and Gender distribution was studied among this population.

Incidence rate

Table 1, Fig. 1 provides the overall hospital-based incidence of orofacial trauma across years. The incidence ranged between 0.60 to 2.77 per 1000 patients across non-pandemic years, while during second wave of pandemic, during 2021, the incidence increased to 7.95 per 1000 patients due reduced number of patients attending the hospital during the pandemic period.

Table 1: Hospital-based incidence of total orofacial trauma across years per 1000 patients

Year	Incidence rate per 1000 patient	95 % CI	
		Lower limit	Upper limit
2012	1.23	0.77	1.86
2013	1.65	1.11	2.35
2014	2.77	2.07	3.63
2015	2.05	1.43	2.85
2016	1.62	1.08	2.32
2017	1.54	1.02	2.24
2018	1.90	1.30	2.68
2019	0.60	0.26	1.18
2020	1.54	0.50	3.58
2021	7.95	5.44	11.23
2022	2.21	1.52	3.10
2023	1.68	1.11	2.44
2024	2.44	1.33	4.09

Figure 1: Line plot with error bars showing incidence rate of orofacial trauma across years per 1000 patients

Age Wise Distribution of Fractures

Patient's age ranged from 7 years to 71 years with a mean age of 26.46 ± 17.10 years. Peak incidence of orofacial trauma was observed in young adults, typically between 2nd and 4th decade of life. (Table 2, Fig. 2)

Table 2: Age wise incidence rate per 1000 Patients

Year	Age (In years)	Cases	Incidence per 1000	95% Lower CI	95% Upper CI
2012	7- 60	22	22.0	12.91	31.09
2013	10- 58	30	30.0	19.43	40.57
2014	19- 65	52	52.0	38.24	65.76
2015	22- 62	35	35.0	23.61	46.39
2016	12-67	27	27.0	16.95	37.05
2017	15-57	27	27.0	16.95	37.05
2018	13-61	32	32.0	21.09	42.91
2019	12-54	8	8.0	2.48	13.52
2020	14-59	5	5.0	0.63	9.37
2021	16-71	32	32.0	21.09	42.91
2022	14-66	33	33.0	21.93	44.07
2023	19-63	26	26.0	16.14	35.86
2024	21-68	14	14.0	6.72	21.28

Figure 2: Line plot with error bars showing age wise incidence rate of orofacial trauma across years per 1000 patients

Gender Wise Distribution of Fractures

In males, the incidence ranged from 0.45 to 2.34 per 1000 patients during non-pandemic years, while during 2021, the incidence increased to 6.71 per 1000 due to reduced number of patients attending the hospital. In females, the incidence ranged between 0.11 to 0.52 per 1000 patients during non-pandemic years, while it increased to 1.24 per 1000 patients. Overall, the incidence was higher in males as compared to females across years. (Table 3, Fig. 3)

Table 3: Gender wise hospital-based incidence orofacial trauma across years per 1000 patients

Year	MALE			FEMALE		
	Incidence rate / 1000 patients	95% CI		Incidence rate / 1000 patients	95% CI	
		Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper
2012	0.84	0.47	1.38	0.39	0.16	0.81
2013	1.54	1.02	2.22	0.11	0.01	0.40
2014	2.34	1.70	3.15	0.43	0.18	0.84
2015	1.70	1.14	2.44	0.35	0.13	0.76
2016	1.39	0.90	2.06	0.22	0.06	0.57
2017	1.31	0.83	1.97	0.23	0.06	0.59
2018	1.48	0.96	2.19	0.42	0.17	0.86
2019	0.45	0.17	0.98	0.15	0.02	0.54
2020	1.23	0.33	3.15	0.31	0.01	1.71

2021	6.71	4.42	9.76	1.24	0.40	2.90
2022	1.74	1.14	2.55	0.47	0.19	0.97
2023	1.31	0.81	2.00	0.37	0.14	0.81
2024	1.91	0.96	3.43	0.52	0.11	1.53

Figure 3: Line plot with error bars showing hospital-based incidence of orofacial trauma across years per 1000 patients

DISCUSSION

Global differences in the distribution of maxillofacial injuries are seen according to topography, community, ethnicity, habitat, and demographic characteristics (gender and age). According to our research, the orofacial injury trends in the central Indian population from 2012 to 2024 was studied. The primary goal of this study was to comprehend how orofacial injuries have changed throughout time. A study by Erol B et al. showed the most common cause of maxillofacial injuries is road traffic accidents with male predilection (77.5%) for facial injuries which is similar to our study.⁹

A study from India by Kumar S et. al. also showed the most common causes of orofacial injuries to be the road traffic accidents followed by fall from height, assault, sports injuries and alcohol influence. The mean age of the patients in this study was 32.43 ± 6.28 which is similar to our study.¹⁰ A study from Davangere, Karnataka by Kamath RA et al. found age of patients with maxillofacial injuries was between the 2nd to 4th decade with male predominance (90.5%) which also correlates with our study. They also found the most common cause as road traffic accidents.¹¹

A study by Khandeparker PV et al. showed a male predilection (80.7%) for maxillofacial injuries similar to our study. It also showed an increasing trend in the age-wise distribution of injuries from the first (1 to 7 years) to the third group (19 to 35 years), followed by a decrease in the incidence in the fourth group (36 to 40 years), a slight increase in the fifth group (41 to 59 years), and a drop-down in the sixth group (> 60 years) based on

the age distribution.¹² A retrospective epidemiological study on maxillofacial trauma in females found a mean age of 31.58 ± 14.32 years and median of 30 years. Highest number (33.8 %) of fractures were sustained in the third decade of life and least (0.7 %) in the eighth decade of life.¹³ These results correlate with our findings.

There was a decline in the incidence of maxillofacial injuries during the covid pandemic years which might be attributed to the travel restrictions imposed during the period leading to reduced road traffic accidents which is a major cause of orofacial trauma.^{14,15} On the contrary, western countries there is a downward trend in the incidence of RTA-related facial fractures, and inter personal violence has become the leading cause. A study on global trends in maxillofacial trauma found consistently high incidence of injuries in the 16- to 30-year-old age group and an increasing proportion of older patients.¹⁶

Various legislative measures can be taken to reduce the incidence of orofacial trauma such as limiting speed limits and night time use of two wheelers, riding while intoxicated must be specifically addressed and restricted by traffic regulations as well as legislative measures, use of helmets and seat belts.¹⁷

CONCLUSION:

Our study concludes that the incidence of orofacial trauma is higher between 2nd to 4th decade with male predominance. The major cause of orofacial trauma in developing countries is road traffic accidents in contrast to developed countries where interpersonal assault is the leading cause. Thus further studies like this will help in better understanding the demographics of orofacial trauma and develop subsequent measures to reduce such incidences.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST:

There is no conflict of interest.

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